

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and Nested Curvatures

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July 7, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series higher terms, it is possible to construct a symmetry and represent particles with higher net curvature as nested curvature of lower magnitude particles. Such a representation is a symmetry of nature, as all we are dealing with is a Lorentz manifold, invoked stationary.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard bosons as net curvature on the matrix tensor. The net curvature are of discrete amounts and is isomorphic to the prime numbers or one. The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The coupling constants series is described in equations (1) to (1.21):

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.21)$$

Now, we can analyze the fifth term in the coupling constants series as an example of nested curvature:

$$[(840 * 11) + (3)] + 11 = 9254 \quad (1.3)$$

$$[(840 * 11) + (3)] + 11 \rightarrow \left[2N_5 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Notice that we can represent the net curvature unbound, i.e. outside of the parenthesis as the following:

$$[(840 * 11) + (3)] + 5 + 5 + 1$$

Alternatively,

$$[(840 * 11) + (3)] + 3 + 3 + 5$$

Since those are equivalent to the net curvature of the fifth term, they can represent the fifth term to be a composite of nested curvature of lower magnitude. We have proven the photon to be associated with $N_V = (+5)$ and the bosons of the weak interaction to be $N_V = (+3)$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow [(8 * 3) + (e)] + \mathcal{W}^+ \quad (2)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (2.1)$$

So the fifth term can be represented the bosonic interactions of the lower coupling terms, nested to one term $N_V = (+11)$:

$$[(840 * 11) + (e)] + g + \gamma + \gamma \quad (3)$$

Two photons and one gluon nested together. Alternatively two \mathcal{W}^+ bosons (can be the minus as well or the Z boson), and one photon, nested exactly to $N_V = (+11)$.

$$[(840 * 11) + (e)] + \mathcal{W}^+ + \mathcal{W}^+ + \gamma \quad (3.1)$$

In other words, take all the composite variations by lower magnitude primes associated with bosons and represent them inside the higher term. It is possible to do with every higher term and solidify the validity of the framework as curvature is all there is. We can think about the higher terms as nested net curvature of different amount. Similar to how we can represent any point in space using a set of independent vectors, we might represent each higher coupling term by a set of independent primes nested together in different combinations. This new coupling term than is an exotic new particle with is a composition of primes of lower magnitude, so despite it is a composition it will appear as a single entity with spin (1) as far as one believes. Below one photon (green) and two W bosons (blue):

Resulting in the new particle associated with the $N_V = (+11)$.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling constants series, Spin Symmetries and Unbounded electrons" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "Proving Einstein Wrong – Gravity is a Short Range Interaction" In: (2021)
- [4] O. Manor. "Light is Gravity" In: (2021)